

Textbook: Focus on Students' National Identity

Blended Learning in Teaching Language for Occupational Purposes: Flexible E-textbook Design

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Abstract

The article analyses the experience of developing an adaptive electronic textbook of French for occupational purposes for the MA programme "Linguistic support of project activities in the field of international cooperation". The authors substantiate the use of the genre-based approach, project-based learning, "flipped classroom" technique and gamification of learning in the design of educational scenarios which can be successfully implemented in the format of traditional, blended and distance learning. In addition, the developed content can be presented via a ready-made virtual educational environment, for example, Moodle, or using a system of disparate blended and distance learning tools. Taking into consideration that the lack of access to equipment and technologies is one of the major risk factors in distance learning introduced in connection with the Covid-19 pandemic, the authors provide a list of tools, depending on their pedagogical function, to be used for implementing designed learning scenarios in various educational contexts. The experience of designing an adaptive electronic textbook and literature review allowed to bring some clarifications in the definition of an e-textbook. It can be considered as a system of teaching content, exercises and tasks, educational scenarios, as well as descriptions of the pedagogical functions of the tools necessary for their implementation. The choice of specific tools that perform one or another pedagogical function should remain with the teacher, depending on concrete educational context.

Keywords: Blended learning tools, electronic textbook design.

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Published by Moscow City University and peer-reviewed under responsibility of TSNI-2021 (Textbook: Focus on Students' National Identity)

Introduction

The Covid-19 pandemic and the restrictions introduced around the world have impacted higher education in

unprecedented ways, accelerating the transition to blended and distance learning and making it more widespread than ever.

Though it has been used in the language teaching domain since early 2000, the concept of blended learning has not yet received one commonly accepted definition. On the contrary, it is sometimes used interchangeably along with the terms "hybrid learning", "mixed learning" or "e-learning" (Tomlinson & Whittaker, 2013). Researchers have tried to differentiate these concepts by introducing percentages indicating parts of face-to-face and distance learning. For example, Smith and Kurten (2007) (as cited in Tomlinson & Whittaker, 2013) describe various forms of co-existence of the two modes of learning as follows:

- web-enhanced learning includes minimal use of online delivery, mainly for administration purposes;
- blended learning includes a far stronger online component, however it does not exceed 45 percent of teaching and learning activities;
- hybrid learning describes the blend in which 45-80 percent of teaching and learning activities are held online;
- fully online is the form of teaching and learning with more than 80 percent of activities conducted online.

Today with the Covid-19 outbreaks causing schools and universities closure it is almost impossible to predict what part of teaching and learning activities will be computer-mediated. Thus, in this paper we will use a broad definition of blended learning: "any combination of face-to-face teaching with computer technology (online and offline activities/materials)." (Tomlinson & Whittaker, 2013). If prior to the pandemic blended learning was rather considered as a choice, today it has become a necessity in order to insure continuity and to build up resilience in higher education in the post-Covid world. Indeed blended learning is considered in many official recommendations as a format with great potential. By combining the best features of face-to-face learning and the potential of ICT, blended learning is conducive to the positive changes of teaching methods [Covid-19 and Higher Education, 2020]. On the other hand, its flexibility results in minimal disruptions in the education process which seems to be crucial in the post-Covid world where blended and online learning should be easily interchangeable when needed (Ambler, Huxley & Peacey, 2020; Dans, 2020). In this regard, the importance of developing adaptable language courses in blended learning format with a strong online component is beyond doubt.

1.2. Blending courses of language for occupational purposes

The flexibility of blended learning makes it an ideal choice for teaching languages for occupational purposes (hereinafter - LOP). The variety of existing professions and the emergence of new ones, the renewal of data and knowledge in all areas of human activity hamper creation of any universal language course books. Due to their delivery via an e-learning environment blended learning courses can be easily updated and usually include a variety of multimedia up-to-date materials relevant for a field of training. Kalugina and others (2018) argue that the following advantages of blended learning are relevant for LOP courses: customised instruction based on needs analysis, enhanced learners' autonomy and multiple opportunities for self-paced learning, easily accessed authentic materials.

Thus, the format itself can be conducive to achieving the main goal of LOP courses which is fostering both components of professional communicative competence. Its professional component “presupposes the mastery of knowledge, skills and abilities characteristic of the given profession” (Cherkashina, 2016) while the linguistic component involves the formation of the skill of using linguistic means to solve professionally oriented communication tasks.

1.3. Electronic textbooks: flexibility as a key advantage.

LOP courses are designed according to a set of principles regardless of the field of training of the learners. Dudley-Evans and St John (1998) (as cited in (Salazar, 2017)) define major characteristics of courses of English for specific purposes as follows: “close relation to the specific needs of the learners, content based on disciplines, occupations and activities, its concern on centering language to those activities”.

Block and others (2020) suggest another set of principles underlying LSP course design which includes knowledge of learners' needs and educational and cultural backgrounds; creation of a classroom culture conducive to efficient and effective learning; meaningful lesson contents which promote language learning and develop critical thinking and learning strategies; adjusting delivery based on constant feedback from learners and analysis of their achievement of learning objectives; constant monitoring and assessing of learners' progress; collaborating with the community of teachers and constant professional development.

These principles can be implemented via an electronic textbook in a blended learning context using a virtual learning environment and a set of underlying teaching techniques for assessment and building a community of learners. Furthermore, electronic textbooks solve the problem of organising disparate authentic resources using the interactive Web 2.0 technologies and enhance active involvement of students in the learning process (Kempe & Grönlund, 2019).

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of this study is to substantiate the structure and teaching techniques underlying the electronic textbook of French for specific purposes which is being designed for MA students of the program "Linguistic support for project activities in the field of international cooperation".

The objectives of the study are:

- to justify the choice of approaches and teaching techniques;
- to describe the structure of the electronic textbook, as well as the tools used to manage the educational process;
- to nuance existing definitions of electronic textbooks in terms of their components.

The need to create a new textbook of French for occupational purposes is due to the following factors:

- 1) Urgent necessity to adapt the traditional face-to-face teaching to the restrictive measures introduced after the Covid-19 outbreak;
- 2) Absence of textbooks of the B2-C1 level which would help to achieve learning objectives set for the MA students. The needs analysis has shown that the field of activity and genres of professional communication of future professionals in project development are at the intersection of business, scientific and advertising discourses. As a result, organising and adapting existing materials takes a lot of time and does not meet all the professional communicative needs.
- 3) Existing textbooks do not satisfy the requirement of a practice-oriented and interdisciplinary approach adopted in the curriculum of the MA program. The MA students are to be able to develop and manage projects in the field of education, tourism, culture and business. The multidisciplinary context makes it impossible to find one textbook with the focus on language for communicating in all of these spheres. Using multiple LOP textbooks is time-consuming both for students and teachers. Moreover, the methodological principles of different textbooks vary considerably.
- 4) In traditional textbooks, the electronic component (a CD or a website) mainly contains exercises for practicing language skills (vocabulary and grammar), as well as multimedia resources for developing listening skills. Therefore, even the most relevant traditional textbooks would not have enough of authentic and up-to-date materials and their content quickly becomes outdated.

Literature review

Terminology used to designate electronic educational resources is not unified, nor does it always have clear definitions. Many terms often overlap which complicates the analysis. Some terms are often used as synonyms of "electronic textbook": "e-books"; "E-learning environment"; "Open educational resources" (OER); "Open textbooks" and "on-line-courses"; "Mobile learning applications" (Kempe & Grönlund, 2019). Thus, it is important to clarify the concept of electronic textbook and highlight its major characteristics which differentiate it from the related terms.

A virtual learning environment is defined as a web based software system which is used for efficient instructional delivery and facilitated communication (JISC, 2009a) as cited in (Barker & Gossman, 2013). The element "software system" in the definition highlights the importance of various tools integrated in a VLE which are used to deliver teaching materials, manage and assess learning activities. However, the term VLE is broader than "electronic textbook" as this software system can be used to create numerous blended learning or online courses which include an electronic textbook as their integral part.

The definition of Open Educational Resources proves this term to be broader than "electronic textbook" as well. OER are defined as "teaching, learning, and research resources that reside in the public domain or have been released under an intellectual property license that permits their free use and re-purposing by others" (Wickline, 2013). Indeed the term OER encompasses all the types of teaching resources including open textbooks, slides, diagrams etc. Another distinction is the open licensing of OER while electronic textbooks can be both open and copyrighted.

Finally, the term "e-book" is defined as "the contents of a book made available in an electronic form" ((Hawkins, 2000) as cited in (Sawyer, 2002)). On the one hand, this term designates books in general, not only textbooks, that is the concept of e-book is broader. On the other hand, it proves to be narrower, as electronic textbooks, according to many definitions which will be analysed further in this paragraph are supposed to include, apart from text, images and other graphic content, tools for communication and advanced text editing.

Having contrasted definitions of similar terms, we will now try to highlight specific features of electronic textbooks and give a comprehensive definition to be used in the present study.

Ratchevsky in (Ratchevsky, 2011) argues that electronic textbooks both in their essence and structure can be considered as an open system due to the fact that they can be easily modified, corrected or supplemented. Functions of an electronic textbook are not limited to simple content delivery, they include assessing students' progress, giving prompt feedback and informing teaching practices in terms of pace and depth of learning via statistical tools. According to Ankudimova and others (2009), electronic textbooks

contain not only information elements, but incorporate software and tools needed to implement educational scenarios designed by their authors.

Similar approach is described in the paper by Kempe & Grönlund (2019) who use the term collaborative digital textbooks to refer to electronic educational resources that contain a set of content components and communication tools with the aim to create a virtual educational environment and manage the interaction between teachers and students, between several students and students' interaction with the content. The tools include software for giving personal feedback, for text manipulation, for monitoring progress and assessing learning outcomes achievement.

Literature review allowed to highlight the following characteristics of electronic textbooks which contrast with the traditional textbooks. Firstly, knowledge can be represented in a wider variety of formats and using different media, which influences both teaching and learning. "Knowledge representations shape, synthesize, emphasize, and communicate complex information in different ways that are embedded in the cDTB (collaborative digital textbooks) designs, and that will have an impact on how teachers and learners can act and interact" (ibid.). Secondly, electronic textbooks give the opportunity to take into account characteristics of the new generation of learners such as constant use of gadgets and the Internet both in everyday life and in learning activities, pragmatic motivation and concentration on immediate and achievable goals (doing homework, passing an exam, getting a good grade) which overshadow global goals (self-improvement, knowledge, development)" (Loseva, 2017). An electronic textbook due to transparent segmentation of the learning content allows students to set clear, quick achievable goals (SMART-learning), whereas the achievement of the latter ultimately leads to fostering necessary competencies.

In this study we will use the following definition suggested by Ankudimova and others (2009): "An electronic textbook is a computer system that contains structured teaching contents and a system of exercises for their comprehension and consolidation, a scenario of learning activities as well as tools designed for its implementation and for independent study of teaching contents using a computer". However it is important to emphasise that the fundamental elements of an electronic textbook, in our opinion, are teaching contents and interaction scenarios designed by teachers in three aspects: student-teacher, student-student, student-content. Software that is used to implement these learning scenarios can vary due to the large number of distance learning tools with similar functionality, requirements of the university authorities in terms of a virtual learning environment to be used and depending on the access of students and teachers to these tools (technical equipment, speed of the Internet connection).

Methodology

The key principles underlying the present study are those of Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL) and of teaching LOP, as well as the fundamental principles of a communicative approach to teaching a foreign language. The main **research methods** are analysis of research papers on blended learning and LOP teaching which has substantiated the principles of the electronic textbook design and structure as well as modeling of the electronic textbook contents.

In accordance with the key principles of blended learning a number of approaches to structuring the electronic textbook content and developing learning scenarios were selected:

- flipped classroom approach to content segmentation;
- modular organisation of training content with additional components for independent study;
- group work and project-based learning used to foster a community of learners;
- frequent low-stake formative assessment as a major type of assessment used to inform content choices, to adapt content delivery and to develop individual learning strategies and personalised feedback.

Genre-based approach was chosen as the main approach to teaching French for occupational purposes in the context of the MA program. By genre-based / genre-oriented approach, we mean “the focus of language education on mastering communication in the genre aspect by purposefully mastering genre forms of everyday, public and / or professional communication based on models of speech genres that are relevant for a particular contingent of students” (Sotova, 2011).

Results

All the considerations mentioned above underlie the structure of the electronic textbook which will be described in this section of the paper. For illustrative purposes we will analyse the unit designed for mastering a specific professional genre related to presentation of project results "*une fiche de synthèse*" (a project summary). This is a concise document, one or two pages long, which briefly summarises project objectives and methodology, context, results and recommendations. Further we will describe the way to segment and present teaching contents, learning scenarios and types of assessment which will form the structure of each unit.

The first stage of learning activities starts in distance mode according to the flipped classroom approach. Students are asked to analyse 2-3 authentic documents and to fill in a table about structural and linguistic features (distance group work). The activity is scaffolded using a set of questions concentrating on

particular linguistic means and their functions and designed by the teacher. For example: *Quels modes utilise-t-on pour décrire le contexte, pour donner des recommandations? Quelles structures syntaxiques sont utilisées pour formuler les objectifs d'un projet? Comment les rendre plus complexes? Quelles formes verbales utilise-t-on pour parler de la méthodologie d'un projet? Quels moyens lexicaux, grammaticaux, syntaxiques, graphiques sont utilisés afin de structurer le texte?* The table is filled according to the principle "from function to form".

The second stage consists of a group discussion of the results in the classroom / during an online meeting, creating a summarising mind map with significant features of the studied genre on a virtual board in mini-groups. Then students complete several grammar exercises (either in oral or in written form) in order to identify grammar and lexical material for revision.

The third stage of teaching and learning scenario aims at fostering professional skills relevant for developing a project which are searching and synthesising information. Students are asked to independently make a selection of texts of the studied genre. After that they receive an assignment with the aim to summarise relevant information on the genre. Working in groups of 2 to 3 people, students present the results of this synthesis in a format of their choice (a PowerPoint presentation, a Wiki page, a virtual whiteboard, a Word document etc.) depending on their access to technologies. This assignment represents the first formative assessment element in the unit. Students' works are assessed both by peers and the teacher according to a set of criteria developed by the teacher. Examples of criteria for peer assessment are: *pertinence des informations sélectionnées, qualité de reformulation, qualité, pertinence de structures linguistiques sélectionnées, qualité visuelle, clarté et structure de la présentation des résultats.*

During the fifth stage students are asked to individually produce a piece in the studied genre with the teacher's guidance in small groups of 2-3 people. Their production must be based on a case study. The teacher offers 3 or 4 documents describing the progress and the results of a project. In the described unit students are offered 2 videos and the link to the main page of the project "Parc éolien en mer de Saint-Nazaire". Having studied the documents, students are supposed to select relevant information and arrange it in accordance with the requirements of the genre. This assignment is the second formative assessment which informs the teacher on students' pace of learning and on the need for a deeper analysis or a revision of the unit key points. As a result, students receive detailed feedback with recommendations for further individual work. Based on these recommendations students prepare for the summative assessment.

The final stage is a summative assessment which consists of producing a *fiche de synthèse* based on a case prepared by the teacher.

The suggested scenario and forms of work can be implemented using the standard virtual educational environment in which the university works, using the most popular applications and programs for distance learning (Zoom, Padlet, Miro), or using software which would be less demanding in terms of the Internet connection speed. While designing the electronic textbook structure we strived to create tasks without a clear reference to a specific technology. Indeed, as shown by a survey of master students at the Faculty of Romance and Germanic Philology of the Voronezh State University, low-speed Internet connection and limited access to online technologies are becoming the most important risk factors in online and blended learning for students (Alexeeva & Buriakova, 2020). Consequently, the task of the authors of teaching materials is to create adaptive learning content that can be delivered using the simplest tools when needed. Thus, it is the pedagogical function of a blended/distance learning tool that should be taken into consideration. In this paper we adopt the pedagogical functions suggested in (Trapp, 2006): presenting information, bi-directional exchange, asynchronous communication, synchronous communication, synchronous cooperation.

The table below summarises the unit structure and suggests a set of technologies that support specific pedagogical functions and can be used interchangeably to deliver content on each stage of the described learning scenario.

Table 1. E-textbook unit structure and suggested learning tools

Learning scenario stage	Pedagogical functions involved	Blended learning		Distance learning	
		Standard VLE	Teacher designed VLE	High-speed Internet connection	Low-speed Internet connection
Independent analyses of pieces of the studied genre	Presenting information	MS Word or PDF files embedded in the course	Cloud storage (Google Drive, Dropbox etc.)	MS Word or PDF files embedded in the VLE or Cloud storage (Google Drive, Dropbox etc.)	Email
Discussion of relevant genre features and identification of lacunae	Presenting information Synchronous cooperation	No tools needed (face-to-face)	No tools needed (face-to-face)	Video Conferencing tools (Zoom, Skype etc.).	Messenger group chat (WhatsApp, Viber, Telegram etc.)
Group work on genre	Presenting information	Wiki-tool	Video Conferencing	Video Conferencing	Messenger group chat for

features (formative assessment)	Synchronous communication Synchronous cooperation	Chat	tools (Zoom, Skype etc.). Virtual whiteboard (Miro, Stormboard etc.)	tools (Zoom, Skype etc.). Virtual whiteboard (Miro, Stormboard etc.)	discussion, MS Word or PDF document for presentation, sent via email
Peer assessment of the previous assignment. Creating a piece of genre in groups	Asynchronous communication. Synchronous communication Synchronous cooperation	No tools needed (face-to-face)	Video Conferencing tools (Zoom, Skype etc.). Google Docs or virtual whiteboards (Miro, Stormboard etc.)	Video Conferencing tools (Zoom, Skype etc.). Google Docs or virtual whiteboards (Miro, Stormboard etc.)	The task is performed individually, the assignment is sent via email
Individual work on a piece of genre. Teacher's feedback	Presenting information Asynchronous communication	MS Word or PDF files embedded in the course	Cloud storage (Google Drive, Dropbox etc.) or a text file (MS Word, PDF etc.) sent by email	Cloud storage (Google Drive, Dropbox etc.) or a text file (MS Word, PDF etc.) sent by email	A text file (MS Word, PDF etc.) sent by email
Summative assessment	Presenting information	No tools needed (face-to-face) or a presentation tool (PowerPoint, Google Slides etc.)	No tools needed (face-to-face) or a presentation tool (PowerPoint, Google Slides etc.)	Video conferencing tools and a presentation tool (PowerPoint, Google Slides etc.)	Presentation tool (PowerPoint, Google Slides etc.). Voice recording tool.

Discussions

We share the idea that "(c)urrent development is sometimes too much driven by technology instead of by pedagogical goals" and that "...the challenge is to reach a deep understanding of the relationship between technological, or even technical, choices and teaching/learning processes" (Dillenbourg, 2000). Therefore, one of the main principles underlying the electronic textbook design is adaptability of the learning scenarios and delivery. All the stages of teaching and learning described above can be implemented either

face-to-face or online with only slight changes. This characteristic of textbook design becomes crucial in the unknown post-Covid world.

In this connection emphasis should be made on the role of tools in the definition of electronic textbook. Similarly to a traditional textbooks containing a teacher's guide with the description of teaching and learning scenarios, an electronic textbook should contain not only teaching contents, but incorporate the description of adopted teaching and learning scenarios and pedagogical functions of tools needed to implement them. A teacher using a traditional textbook takes authors' recommendations into consideration. However, he/she is free to adapt these teaching and learning scenarios to a particular educational context taking into consideration learners' background and prior knowledge, number of teaching hours available and many other factors. Adopting the same approach by describing pedagogical functions of blended/distance learning tools to be used and, probably, recommending several from the existing range, authors of electronic textbooks give the teachers' the same freedom to bring necessary changes in the concrete educational context. Teachers' choices of particular blended/distance learning tools and of ways to implement designed teaching contents can be viewed as a key difference between an electronic textbook and an e-learning course.

The flexibility of electronic format of the textbook enhances the quality of teaching and learning and allows a more efficient achievement of learning objectives in teaching languages for occupational purposes due to a number of factors:

- more opportunities for group work and interaction with content;
- more flexibility in terms of the depth of coverage of lexical and grammar points taking into account the individual needs of students;
- bringing into focus types of assignments relevant for the future professional activity including search and synthesis of information as well as development of important soft skills;
- introducing a variety of digital formats of materials that students can share with each other;
- more opportunities to get personalised feedback both from peers and teachers, more opportunities for development of individual learning scenarios.

Thus, the potential of the electronic textbook in LOP teaching is quite promising in the context of the MA program "Linguistic support of project activities in the field of international cooperation" and the results of

its implementation using standard VLEs or VLEs created by teachers will become the focus of further studies.

Conclusion

The concept of e-textbook, despite the wide use both of the term and the artifact it designates, remains vague and is frequently used interchangeably with such terms as e-book, e-learning course, OER etc. Authors' experience of developing adaptive teaching contents for a course of French for occupational purposes in the field of project management has allowed clarifying several major characteristics of an electronic textbook. In terms of teaching and learning contents it should provide multimedia materials and a system of exercises, tasks and assignments. The methodological component of an e-textbook is supposed to contain descriptions of the designed learning scenarios, techniques and approaches, as well as presentation of pedagogical functions of the tools to be used while implementing these scenarios. Finally, underlying learning scenarios should enhance the flexibility of e-textbook as a major component of blended and distance learning and give the teachers a choice of concrete tools depending on learners' needs, access to technology, recommended VLE and the model of the blend used in their classroom.

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